

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

AZERBAIJAN'S TOURISM INDUSTRY'S EXPERIENCE WITH CUTTING-EDGE TRENDS

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Abstract

Tourism is one of the most important areas of activity of the modern economy, aimed at meeting the needs of people and improving the quality of life of the population. At the same time, unlike many other sectors of the economy, tourism does not lead to the depletion of natural resources. Being an export-oriented sphere, tourism shows greater stability compared to other industries in an unstable situation in world markets. The concept of innovation refers to both radical and gradual (incremental) changes in the products, processes and strategy of the organization (innovative activity). Based on the fact that the purpose of innovation is to increase the efficiency, cost-effectiveness, quality, customer satisfaction of the organization, the concept of innovation can be identified with the concept of entrepreneurship - vigilance for new opportunities to improve the work of the organization (commercial, government, charitable).

Keywords: innovative activity, innovation, natural resources, domestic tourism.

Innovation is the result of investing in the development of obtaining new knowledge, an innovative idea for updating the spheres of people's lives (technology; products; organizational forms of existence of society, such as education, management, labor organization, service, science, informatization, etc.) and the subsequent process of implementation (production) of this, with a fixed receipt of additional value (profit, lead, leadership, priority, fundamental improvement, qualitative superiority, creativity, progress) [6.-page 128]

Innovation is considered from different perspectives: in relation to technology, commerce, social systems, economic development and policy formulation. Accordingly, there is a wide range of approaches to the conceptualization of innovations in the scientific literature.

To distinguish innovation from the concepts listed above, it is often specified that the peculiarity of innovation is that it allows you to create additional value, allows the innovator to obtain additional value and is associated with implementation. In this view, an innovation is not an innovation until it has been successfully implemented and has begun to be useful.

An alternative approach uses other terms as part of the definition of innovation: "Innovation occurs when someone uses an invention - or uses something that already exists in a new way - to change the way people live." In this case, the invention may be a new concept, device or other things that facilitate activities, and innovation is not associated with whether the organizer of the innovation received any benefit and whether it brought a positive effect.

When conceptualizing the concept of innovation, it is useful to compare it with other concepts. In particular, in the scientific literature it is noted that the concept of "innovation" is often confused with the concept of "invention", denoting the creation of a new technical development or the improvement of an old one. In addition, many product and service

improvements would be better described simply as "improvement." The concepts of "change" and "creativity" can also sometimes be used instead of the concept of "innovation" [9.- 64page].

The innovation process is a gradual adoption of innovations in tourism.

The most promising direction is the creation of centers of cultural, scientific, educational, tourist activities on the basis of archaeological, ethnographic, architectural, natural landscape (and, in the best case, complex) open-air museums. A wealth of experience in creating such facilities has been accumulated in foreign countries (Flevopark in Holland, Lejre in Denmark, Butser Hill in England, Dyuppel in Germany, Pamunkey in the USA).

A fundamentally new direction is the inclusion of tourists, vacationers, visitors to theatrical performances and role-playing games in the service. This also includes the reconstruction of historical and cultural situations of different times. At the same time, viewers have the opportunity to become direct participants in the interactive process.

This direction may be associated with extreme entertainment and activities, such as hiking, expeditions, experiments, etc. of varying degrees of difficulty.

Currently, there is a huge number of completely new tourist destinations: ethnographic, archaeological, floristic; offers of photo tours, military tours, wine tours, religious and wedding tours are brought to the tourist market. Medical, educational, ecological and other types of cultural and educational tourism are developing, new museums are appearing, including private ones, with the possibility of introducing individual programs.

Against this background, the introduction of innovations contributes not only to the development of the areas under consideration, but also to the harmonization of the relationship of modern man with society and nature.

Socio-cultural service and tourism are designed to solve many problems: recreational, educational, educational, the task of preserving, studying and using the natural and historical and cultural heritage. They are also permanent, significant (and for some regions, the main) sources of income, solve the problem of creating jobs, etc.

Therefore, the introduction of innovations contributes not only to the development of the areas under consideration, but also to the harmonization of the relationship of modern man with society and nature.

The main goals of creating centers of cultural, scientific, educational, tourist activities are the development and implementation of a new model of cultural activity in the region by creating an interactive communication zone on the problems of the history, culture and art of ancient societies and civilizations, their role and place in the world historical process, as well as their impact on the modern world. However, the activities of such centers are not limited to human history and culture. Communicating with nature, studying it, as well as solving the problems of the relationship between nature and man, fostering respect for the environment can and should also be included in the scope of such a center. In general, we can say that one of the main goals of such institutions should be the greening of human life in the broadest sense of the word.

Respect for nature, love for it, competent environmental behavior of a person have become a necessary condition for the survival of mankind on our beautiful planet. Initiation to nature makes it possible to introduce a person to humanity, common sense, beauty, harmony with nature and with oneself.

The word "ecology" comes from the Greek words *oikos* - "house" and *logos* - "concept, teaching" Ecology in the broad sense of the word - knowledge about the environment in which a person lives: from the immediate environment to the scale of the universe and knowledge about oneself.

It is unlikely that our life can be healthy and harmonious without preserving the natural and cultural heritage. It is very important to acquaint a person from early childhood with the House in which he lives. But no matter how much information people remember, in the absence of a subtle feeling and perception of the world, without love for this world in all its manifestations, this knowledge will not become creative.

Modern problems of the relationship of a person with himself, his own kind and with the environment can be solved only if the ecological worldview is formed in all people, their environmental awareness and culture are improved, and the need to implement the principles of sustainable development is understood.

Work on the creation of integrated centers involves the activation and introduction of new forms of cooperation with state and public organizations, museums, research centers and individuals. The use of these forms, as well as new technologies, including information technologies, will not only provide access to a fundamentally new level of cultural, educational,

exposition, exhibition, and tourism activities, will create a recreational zone of a fundamentally new type, will help expand the audience, but also will make the center a very promising resource source with practically unlimited possibilities.

The main tasks of the center:

1. Creation of a center of culture, science, education, development of a fundamentally new type.

2. Prevention of destruction of monuments of nature, history and culture and their preservation for posterity.

3. Implementation of the role of a generator of public initiatives in the field of protection of natural, historical and cultural monuments and the environment in general.

The cultural and educational direction includes the creation of an open-air museum. Rich experience in this direction has been accumulated abroad. The movement to create them dates back to the 1960s. The historical and archaeological research center established in 1962 in Lejre (Denmark), which at first functioned as a scientific and experimental institution, can be considered a pioneer here. On a plot of 25 hectares in Leira, in the Gerthadalen valley, 40 km from Copenhagen, a "prehistoric village" was built, as well as educational, administrative and other buildings. Experimenters plowed small fields with wooden plows, acquired herds of the simplest types of domestic animals. Their meat, as well as the fruits of the fields, served as the main food.

At first, only archaeologists with their closest assistants were engaged in recreating the village of the early Iron Age and the ancient way of life. But in 1970, they got the idea to invite some ordinary Danish families to live for a week or two in a prehistoric village. Initially, the members of these families lived in the "prehistoric" village only in the summer. They learned how to make pottery, work the fields and harvest, churn butter, smoke cheeses, dress leather, spin wool and fiber, and weave. Then they tried to live in Iron Age houses during the winter. By their own admission, the participants really had the feeling that they were closer to the state in which people were 2000 years ago.

Following the example of the complex in Leira, a similar center was created in Duppel (Germany) Here, under the guidance of Leir instructors, a Slavic and Germanic settlement of the second half of the 12th - early 13th centuries was built with medieval tools. In addition to conducting purely scientific experiments to recreate "medieval life", the center's employees actively attract everyone to Duppel. Suffice it to say that much in the Dyuppel village was built by the hands and at the expense of hundreds of selfless enthusiasts, most of whom are not directly related to scientific activity. Some urban families come to Dyuppel for quite a long time and adapt to the medieval environment. The number of people who want to visit the village in Düppel far exceeds its ability to satisfy the interest of everyone.[9.-64page]

The example of Leire and Duppel "infected" many. So, in 1975, a small group of Dutch people, consisting of ten adults, the oldest of whom was 72

years old at that time), and four children (the youngest of them was only two years old), under the guidance of the teacher Roelof Gorreus de Haas, tried to recreate those the conditions in which their ancestors lived, as well as to experience for themselves all the "charms" of ancient life.

The Stone Age was chosen as a model. Enthusiasts approached the matter very thoroughly. They studied all the literature at their disposal, and also got acquainted with the expositions of various archaeological sites and museums. Having made a fairly complete picture of the methods of activity of people of the Stone Age, they began to select a place for the experiment. The choice fell on the Flevopark polder. However, before embarking on the implementation of a complex and time-consuming experiment, all participants regularly conducted training trips to the polder for several years, during which they imitated the life of ancient people.

Finally, the solemn moment arrived. The group arrived at the Flevopark polder, taking with them tools made in ancient ways, household equipment, everyday items, only natural products in the form of grains and beans, several goats, a ram and a dog. For housing, participants in the experiment built seven huts with hearths inside from tree trunks, twigs, bark and clay coating. In addition to residential buildings, a barn for cattle with a wicker fence, a barn for stocks of grain, hay, firewood and other household supplies were built. A well and storage pits were also dug. An earthen oven was built for baking bread.

For the whole summer the small collective lived a primitive life. The villagers cultivated tiny fields with stone hoes, ground grain on stone grain grinders, prepared fodder for livestock, cooked food on the hearth, made fabrics on looms, dressed leather, made various tools, molded and fired ceramic vessels, etc.

The experiment lasted for several years and brought a lot of impressions and discoveries to both its participants and specialists.

In our country, the creation of such active open-air museums began relatively recently.

Baku is the capital of Azerbaijan, a large and very beautiful city, as well as a popular tourist destination located on the shores of the Caspian Sea. It is rich in its history, impresses vacationers with architectural and natural sights, and surprises with modern infrastructure. You can come here for both beach and cultural recreation, but the main thing that delights all guests of Baku is the old city, called Icheri Sheher.

Icheri Sheher is an old quarter, which since 1977 has been an architectural and historical reserve. It is located in the central part of Baku, on a small hill, territorially within the Sabail region. Its area occupies a little over 220 thousand square meters. m. and includes not only places of cultural significance, but also ordinary houses inhabited by ordinary local residents. It was around this quarter, surrounded by powerful fortress walls, that the whole of Baku was gradually built and expanded.

It is worth noting that Icheri Sheher is the first object of the republic, which was included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. It happened in 2000

and served as a massive influx of tourists. Currently, the place is included in the list of popular resorts in Europe. Undoubtedly, there is something to do and see here.

In addition to the architectural monuments that have survived to this day in the form of towers, churches, mosques and other buildings that appeared during the reign of the shahs, the area is interesting because it is surrounded by a modern metropolis with a superbly developed infrastructure. In the neighborhood of narrow streets and ancient dwellings, there are beautiful high-rise buildings, respectable hotels, entertainment venues, restaurants, and a magnificent promenade..

A few tens of kilometers from Baku, on the Absheron Peninsula, there is a unique open-air archaeological and ethnographic museum "Gala" - a complex that has collected five thousand years of history.

The archaeological and ethnographic museum complex Gala was established in 2008 on the territory of the ancient village of Gala located in the Khazar region of Baku with the assistance of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation. Museum visitors can get acquainted with the ancient history of the village of Gala. In the Gala Archaeological and Ethnographic Museum Complex, one of the few open-air museums, the lifestyle of the population living in the Gala village from the 3rd millennium BC to the present day, mounds, tombs, residential buildings, the ruins of an ancient castle, 5 mosques, 3 bathhouses, etc. The pottery and bakery work today in the same way as in the Middle Ages. The Gala memorial complex exhibits ancient human settlements on rocks and caves dating back to the Bronze Age, rock paintings, ancient foundations, ruins of an ancient wall dating back to the X-XIV and X-XV centuries, two underground passages going in the direction of the Caspian Sea and the city of Baku, tendir dating back to the 18th century, gavaldash, ceramic products, household items and jewelry, weapons and coins, preserved ruins of an ancient settlement. Since 2011, the Gala Information Center, the Ethno-Ecological Center, the Museum of Antiques and the caravanserai-restaurant have been operating on the territory of the Gala Museum Complex.

The creation of open-air museums in the liberated territories of Azerbaijan will be of great historical significance. Open-air museums should demonstrate both moments of racism and ethnic cleansing against our people, as well as acts of vandalism committed over the past 28 years of modern history, and also provide visitors with a detailed information about the events that took place in this period of time. It should be noted that the creation of a museum will attract more attention where the ruins of buildings and structures are located more and more closely. An example is the relevant parts of the Istisu medical complex, the cities of Aghdam, Zangilan, Fizuli, Jabrayil, and in places with a small population - mosques, shrines. The complex of archaeological monuments illegally exploited by Armenians on the territory of Shahbulag in the Aghdam region and the Azykh cave in the Khojavend region will be of great importance from a historical point of view.

Restoration of the protected area of 350 hectares, the cradle of Azerbaijani culture, the city of Shusha, will turn it into an open-air museum.

Conclusion

The theoretical and experimental work carried out on the problem of innovation in the field of tourism allows us to assert that the goals and objectives set for the thesis work have been achieved. This fact is confirmed by the following findings:

According to the forecasts of Azerbaijani experts, in the next 10-15 years, tourism, under certain accompanying conditions, could have a significant positive impact on the economy of the country and its large cities.

The crisis, which negatively affected all enterprises of the Azerbaijani tourism industry without exception, has one positive side: despite the drop in demand for services in general, the reduction in the staff of qualified employees and the reduction in labor costs and marketing activities, the interest of Azerbaijanis in domestic tourism has noticeably increased.

In the context of the ongoing crisis, many travel agencies are forced to look for non-traditional options and methods for solving their problems, one of which is the problem of informatization.

The results of a study of the market of tourism innovative technologies and an analysis of the activities of a number of tourism companies showed that Azerbaijan is far behind the countries that have advanced the most in the field of tourism.

It also showed that the central place among modern information and computer technologies in tourism is occupied by automated booking systems integrated with the Internet.

The implementation of innovative technologies in Azerbaijan is possible with:

- creation of conditions for dynamic and sustainable economic growth;
- improving the level and quality of life of the population by increasing the availability of tourist services, employment and incomes of the inhabitants of our country;
- increasing the competitiveness of the Azerbaijan economy by increasing the attractiveness of our country as a tourist destination;

- ensuring a balanced socio-economic development of the constituent entities of the Azerbaijan by increasing the share of tourism in the regional gross product.

Taking into account the nature of Azerbaijan tourist resources, the state of the tourist infrastructure and the readiness of the tourist product, the following types of tourism can be of particular interest for the development of inbound tourism in our country: cultural, educational, business, as well as specialized tourism (event, ecological, hunting and fishing, active, including in the future skiing, extreme (adventure), ethnic etc.).

For the domestic market, it is especially important to develop beach and health tourism.

For Azerbaijan, with its underdeveloped tourism infrastructure and huge unclaimed tourism potential, the development of specialized tourism as a new alternative direction is of the greatest interest in terms of attracting a sophisticated foreign consumer and diversifying the domestic tourism offer. The identified priority types of tourism and promising tourist regions determine their respective priorities in the development of tourism infrastructure.

References:

1. Gulyaev VG Organization of tourist activities: 1996.
2. Gulyaev V.G. "New information technologies in tourism". 1999.
3. Dekhtyar G.M. "Tourism industry: Legal acts: Legal status of foreign citizens in the Russian Federation. International documents. Conventions", 2005.
4. Zhdanova E.I. Management and economics in show business. 2003
5. Zdorov A.B. The economics of tourism. Textbook. 2007
6. Prostakov Ivan Foreign terms in the tourist industry: A brief explanatory dictionary / 2008.
7. Romanov A.N. Marketing. / Ed. A.N. Romanova. - M.: Banks and stock exchanges, 1996.
8. Sviridenko S.S. "Information and information technologies in modern society". 1993.
9. Senin V.S. Tourism: mini-dictionary. 2nd ed., revised and additional. (Pocket allowance). - 2008. -
10. Sister G. "The strategic importance of information and the role of databases in marketing". J. Problems of the theory and practice of management, , 1997,